

Remarks on Doctor Rocco Gangle's Conference about "Heidegger's Semiotics"

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The following summarizes the main points of my remarks:

1. The concept of "Sign" is criticized by Heidegger because it supposes an instrumental view of language, proper to metaphysics, one which began with Stoicism. He counterposes to it a phenomenological and ontological view of language, centered on "meaning" and not on "signification", and referring being and not only beings, more precisely, showing being's essentiality. He approaches "Zeichen" (sign) to "zeigen" (show) and this to "sagen" (say), a perspective which was common to Greek's thought and literature until Aristoteles. As a matter of fact, he adds, already in the primitive worldview, "sign is always what is shown", there is a coincidence between the two: it has a symbolic character (*Sein und Zeit*, § 17, 82). Man, the speaker, is not yet separated from reality, he himself is "in-the-world" (in-der-Welt).
2. Nevertheless, in the context of "Dasein's Analytics", Heidegger uses the concept of sign in order to show how man understands beings, not as a thing in itself, a "substance", but as a "reference" (Verweisung) to something. That is to say, pointing to a larger context of relations and, at last, to a final horizon of meaning, the one which he names the "world" (*Ibidem*).
3. The appropriate approach to clarify man's relation to being is not "intentionality", always supposing an epistemic and predicative view, but "being-in-the-world", that is to say the ontological structure of Dasein. This last one is the being which we ourselves are, the one which has a relation of being to his own being and to being in general, being therefore an openness where Being itself appears (*Sein und Zeit*, §§ 4, 5 and 12). The concept of "Worldliness" (Weltlichkeit) points to the horizontal-transcendental character of this appearance, which "speech" (Rede) articulates as "meaning" (Sinn; *SZ*, § 18). That is the reason why, in my opinion, a semantic approach is more appropriate than a semiotic one, all depending of course on the way these terms are intended.

4. About the famous “Kehre”, I should say H. II is already present in H. I, as he himself affirms (Cf. *HumanismusBrief*), with the correspondent primordially of Being, history and even poetry (Cf. *SZ*. § 29).
5. The “Ereignis” of “Seyn” appropriates man’s thought revealing itself as “Sage” (Saying), he presents itself as meaningful, and this is the very proper origin of human language (Sprache; conf. *Unterwegs zur Sprache*). And language gives man the world where man dwells.
6. In conclusion, “man is in a hermeneutical relation to language”, which shows itself as the historical saying/showing of Being, and only because of this is he able to speak.